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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

La persona mayor como ser humano en la ejecución del encarcelamiento en las prisiones checas - sondeo exploratorio

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Resumen

Con el envejecimiento de la sociedad se prevé un aumento de las personas mayores que cometen delitos y de la ejecución de los procesos de encarcelamiento no sólo en la República Checa. Basándonos en la evidencia de la literatura publicada y en sondeos exploratorios realizados, destacamos la oportunidad y la necesidad de prestar más atención a las personas mayores; hacemos un llamamiento a un cambio de actitud hacia la población de edad avanzada y, principalmente, hacia las personas mayores en la ejecución de la pena de prisión. El trabajo pretende arrojar luz teórica y a través de notas de campo sobre aspectos concretos relacionados con este grupo de personas. Se llevaron a cabo seis entrevistas y se revisaron archivos personales para aportar datos y características interesantes sobre este grupo. Con respecto a la creciente población de personas mayores en ejecución penitenciaria, existe una necesidad obvia de analizar este grupo en mayor profundidad, no sólo a través de la lente de las ciencias sociales, sino también proporcionando un apoyo y una atención más profundos. Además, el proceso de envejecimiento en prisión exige una mayor necesidad de cualificación y capacidad de los empleadores para proporcionar una atención adecuada. Además, existe una importante necesidad de reorganizar la financiación.

Palabras clave: Envejecimiento, ejecución penitenciaria, envejecer, calidad de vida, prisión.

Abstract

An older person as a human in the execution of imprisonment in Czech prisons – exploratory probe

The eldering of society is expected to see growth in elderly people conducting crime and in the execution of imprisonment processes not only in the Czech Republic. Based on evidence from published literature and conducted exploratory probes, we highlight the chance and need for more attention paid to older people; we call for a change of attitude towards the eldering population and mainly towards older people in the execution of imprisonment. The paper aims to shed light in theory and through field notes on specific related towards this group of people. The six interviews were conducted, and personal files were reviewed to bring interesting insights and characteristics about this group. With regard to the growing population of older people in the execution of imprisonment, there is an obvious need to analyze this group in more depth, not only through the lens of social science but also by providing deeper support and care. Further, the eldering

process in imprisonment demands a bigger need for employers' qualification and ability to provide adequate care. Plus, there is a significant need to reorganize funding.

Keywords: Eldering, execution of imprisonment, growing old, life quality, prison

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1. Introduction

Expansion of the length of life is expected to bring up higher expectations related to maintaining a good quality of life. This topic is and will be more relevant for societies around the world as more older people are living up to older age. The expansion of demographic changes in the 21st century provides Europe with more possibilities in areas related to elderly people, not only in the process of imprisonment but also in older people with diverse handicaps. These changes can be perceived as the provision of adequate health and social care but also as a challenge. The current generation of older people is healthier than the previous generations, but older people require more diverse and specific health and social care. Let us now consider older people in the context of Czech's prison system – in the context of this paper, we discuss elderly people in the execution of imprisonment.

Older people are the biggest group in our society, which has specifics that need to be reflected in their attitude towards and care for them. Even though we can expect that the ability to take care of themselves will be longer within this group with the next generation of seniors, the next generation growing up to the elderly age will have a significant influence on the whole society (Ondrusova, Krahulcova et al., 2020). The statistical prognosis 2040 is that almost 25% of the Czech population will be older. This will be caused by the elderying process of the baby boom generation from the 70s 20th century (Ondrusova, Krahulcova et al., 2020).

The older people in the execution of imprisonment face similar issues as other older people. However, they must face this issue in a more extreme environment, which is not suitable for this. Society's elderying is logically influencing these groups and prisoners as well.

2. The number of elder people in the execution of imprisonment

The formal age line is 65 years and long-term inability to work, thus being involved in employment. This is the definition of "long-term work unable", where older people of higher age are included. This is not an exclusive group for older people, but we can meet older people in other groups in this group, not only older people. Even though these groups exist, age is not defined (Vidoviciva, Wija, 2020).

Without regard to numbers and statistical information, this population seems to grow not only in the European context but also within a combination of many factors. Mainly, it is the combination of demographic, socioeconomic and legal factors. Not only does the 'silver tsunami' affect us, but also the economic crisis, growing poverty, and inequality (ACLU, 2012).

According to the Statistical Yearbook of Prison Service of the Czech Republic 2022 (2023), the age structure of defendants, with regards to higher age, follows:

Table 1
Age structure of defendants

	male	female	total
under 50 years	153	14	167
under 55 years	92	8	100
under 60 let years	70	5	75
under 65 years	26	5	31
under 70 years	17	1	18
under 75 years	3	0	3
under 80 years	2	1	3

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Prison Service of the Czech Republic 2022 (2023)

Total number of defendants to 31st December 2022 was 1 438 (1 323 male and 115 female). In context of people over 50 years it was 230 defendant (210 male and 20 female).

According to Statistical yearbook of Prison service of Czech Republic 2022 (2023) the age structure of sentenced, with regards to higher age, follows:

Table 2
Age structure of the sentenced

	male	female	total
under 50 years	2 031	166	2 197
under 55 years	1 237	91	1 328
under 60 years	768	55	823
under 65 years	390	24	414
under 70 years	215	23	238
under 75 years	71	8	79
under 80 years	32	0	32
over 80 let	6	2	8

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Prison Service of the Czech Republic 2022 (2023)

Total number of sentenced to 31st December 2022 was 17 498 (16 012 male and 1 486 female). In context of people over 50 years it was 2 922 sentenced (2 719 male and 203 females).

According to Statistical yearbook of Prison service of Czech Republic 2022 (2023) the age structure of life sentenced with regards to higher age, follows: Total number of lives sentenced to 31st December 2022 was 47 (44 male and 3 female) In context of people over 50 years it was 26 lives sentenced (24 male and 2 female). In a study conducted by Martinkova and Biedermanova (2019), they presented the crimes their respondents had committed. Older people were more likely to commit less serious crimes, such as stealing or obstruction of legal activities, which made up to half of the crimes they committed. On the other hand, older people in our probe conducted serious crimes as well, such as murder, or tried to murder someone (almost 13%). The most alarming is the fact that those who conducted the serious crime have not been in their entire life legally taken to court (offenders of four murders and one rape) (Martinkova and Biedermanova, 2019).

3. The needs and specifics

The needs and issues related to older prisoners appear in diverse areas, mainly health and social care. In this perspective, Snyder et al. (2019) speak about biopsychological care needs where physical, social and psychological needs are related and affect each other. In the background of biopsychological needs is also the lack of specific and customized care for elderly imprisoned people.

The needs of this group can be observed from many angles. For example, in literature (ACLU, 2012; Branham, 2010; Human Rights Watch, 2012; Upton, 2014), the questions focus on practical and material needs and issues such as health care (including addiction issues), work and education. Significantly, they highlight the issue or relation and social contacts. Other resources (Snyder et al., 2009) more significantly stress the task of social care workers in the background of the structural needs of this group. This is related to the issue of discrimination of minority groups in prison (Snyder et al., 2009). This environment is more suitable for younger people (mostly male prisoners). However, it is also about the stigma of ex-prisoners and the lack of possibilities to be part of society. This includes thinking about ethical questions such as the "right of offenders for organ transplantation or expensive treatment of cancer" (Branhman, 2010). Another issue related to the legislation is sometimes outdated, and it leads to necessary long sentences (ACLU, 2012).

Therefore, this opens discussion not only for social workers working in prisons but also for reflection of senior workers and related management of the prison system. Social work with people conducting crimes is happening on more levels according to their sentence level. It keeps happening throughout the imprisonment and when there is an alternative sentence. Hanzelova (2020) describes the prison environment in the context of work with sentences, which sets higher demands on social workers in social and psychological areas, crisis intervention, and medication. The basic requirement is empathy and acceptance of the sentenced person as they are, the ability of individual attitude. Plus, the ability to alter help and not follow the existing system.

Here, we can support Danek's (2022) thought that there will be a strong need to support cross-disciplinary knowledge and cooperation. The resorts of equality, education, social support, and health all need to strengthen and begin to cooperate. During team cooperation, it is crucial that we can understand, cooperate, and build relationships with other team members. Every member of the team is a unique help for the team. Thus, the cross-area team could be a significant help.

Diverse studies show that prisoners are, in general, less healthy and mobile than their age group members. They are more often ill and have health problems. Prisoners are more likely to have psychological issues than the general population. Snyder et al. (2009) highlight the psychological and health issues. In their study, James and Glaze (2006) mention the percentage, which is more than twice higher than in the general population. According to their findings, the prisoners need to talk about crimes, issues, fears and worries related to their relationships, depression and traumas. Half of older prisoners in the UK have at least one psychological issue (ACLU, 2012). This includes depression, addiction (alcohol and drug use), and psychological issues such as dementia, schizophrenia, phobia ... Psychological issues and mainly starting dementia are not acknowledged by guards. One of the most needed attributes to survive in prison is discipline and good manners, which is the only way to avoid disciplinary penalties (Maschi, Kwak et al., 2012). There is a big chance that prison workers will interpret psychological issues as issues with discipline, and often, it will be followed by penalties. To give behavioural sanctions to a person with dementia is not a good idea as regards their health condition.

Humblet and Decorte (2013), based on the literature review, present a list of topics which can be situated on the needs of older prisoners:

- ✓ Prison infrastructure;
- ✓ Social and health care;
- ✓ Relationships with other prisoners;
- ✓ Relationships with prison's employees and workers;
- ✓ Loneliness and isolation;
- ✓ Daily activities and work;
- ✓ Prison regime;
- ✓ Return to society.

The following areas of issue that we present are not only related to this group. Aging is a natural physiological process that involves a number of changes affecting the organism. Changes in the physical field are reflected in education primarily by worsening resistance to adverse and disruptive influences, loss of energy, by reducing sensory capacity (Španteková, Smékalová, 2015).

In the process of growing old, we can acknowledge several changes that do not apply to all older people. The most influential factor is health, one of the criteria defining ageing. However, it does not mean these changes must be blindly accepted, and we

cannot fight them. It is important to accept that tiredness is part of life. Similarly, the changes in skin or changes in sense functions such as hearing or vision are normal. The majority of these changes happen gradually. Lower sensitivity of vision, hearing, or tiredness can be reflected in one's behaviour and/or mood.

In many cases, changes occur in lower forms and can cause issues, but can we do something about it? The issue can worsen, and ageing can become problematic. The issues with diverse organs occur, cooperation between organs can become problematic, and other serious illnesses can occur.

The common health issues include obesity. This physiological change is often connected to lower administration of energy. If individuals keep consuming the same amount of nutrition, they get fat. The question about enough movement is still questioned about older prisoners. There is agreement that obesity is unhealthy for the heart and veins (Malkova, Krch, 2001). For individuals with obesity, it is good to use diverse reduction diets. It is crucial to acknowledge that diet does not mean hunger but it focuses on health and nutritionally rich food.

For obesity, we can observe malnutrition or insufficient nutrition. A loss of taste or teeth might cause this. Further, it is important to reflect on the worsened digestive and mobility limitations or usage of medicaments, which can cause loss of feeling hungry. Also, the digestive system is less able to absorb all nutrition. Therefore, the food regime is important; eating less but more frequently is better. In food, it is also important to remember the drinking regime.

We cannot forget the importance of movement, which positively influences the body's development and the overall feeling of an individual. A good example of activities for older people is walking or music-supported workouts. The negative side of growing old is falls and injuries. These can cause issues while taking care of oneself. An individual does not have enough strength and maybe cannot walk, but they might be able to stand and support themselves with their hands. Unfortunately, pain is part of movement after an injury.

Therefore, it is important to consider the change of mobility, which can cause the prisoner to be unable to move. The inability to move causes a lot of issues. For example, the obesity above causes bad blood circulation and digestive habits. During long-term lying and sitting, decubitus can occur. To prevent this, it is good to use diverse pillows. Worsening of mobility causes loss of movement, which is a strong interruption of one's life, not only prisoners. Surrounding – the environment should customize itself for one to move around. One of these changes can be diverse exercises, which should be done so individuals can do something for themselves.

Regarding movement, there is a strong link with materials such as handles, adjustable beds and good chairs, beds with correct high adjustments and other important tools that can help with movement, regeneration, and everyday life.

Personal hygiene is one of the easiest factors to control. It includes mainly the overall body care, nutrition, and other hygiene problems of eating the wrong food or drinks. Also, the regime of rest is important. We cannot forget soul and sexual hygiene to live harmonically and well (Kvapilik, Cerna, 1990).

Hygiene is a crucial part of one's ability to care for oneself. Of course, hand washing is part of everyday care due to the possibility of the appearance of diverse diseases. Older people find it hard to change their attitudes and traditions, such as caring for their face, hair, mouth and teeth. Nowadays, there is a big market for diverse textiles and shoes, which makes it easier. We would like to mention the care after one's teeth, which is often a significant issue. Often, older people might have decayed teeth, or there is an insufficient number of teeth. Significant influence on teeth and their quality has medicaments which older people consume. Frequent medical check-ups should prevent these issues.

Another issue is incontinence, which can confuse older individuals. They might react like that as they think this issue is related to children. Therefore, this can cause emotional distress and physical unhappiness as the time for hygiene prolongs. The help is easy; it is the usage of materials against incontinence.

Ageing also negatively influences sense organs (vision, hearing, taste, smell, and sensitivity) within the sense of lower enjoyment of things happening around us. Given a stimulus, it needs a longer time to travel to the brain and to activate the nervous system. Therefore, elderly people might be discouraging dons when they need to react more promptly.

During ageing, the vision quality is lowered, especially for older people. Older people's eyes need more light to function properly. Some diverse situations and sights signal issues with vision, such as wanting to touch something and missing it or not managing daily tasks as well as they would like to. The usage of glasses can very often manage lower vision.

Another organ that very often causes some issues is the ears. Similarly, as with vision, it is good to regularly check up on hearing abilities. Lower hearing can be displayed by loss of interest and by passivity. Further, the lower hearing abilities can lead to loss of social contact as it becomes hard for an individual to follow the conversation. To secure all needs within hearing, we use hearing aids. Teaching an individual how to work with a hearing aid is crucial. The transition towards this aid is hard for an individual they did not hear before, and now they hear too much, which can lead towards a higher level of tiredness. Without regard to the ward hearing aid, it is crucial to speak clearly. An individual might want to see the mouth clearly to read lips.

Smell and taste are other senses that might get worse with age. The cause is the degradation of these organs. We cannot accept that with loss of taste, one stops eating.

We cannot forget to mention the lower quality of fine motor skills. Fine motor skills can be lower due to rheumatic illness or Parkinson's disease. Still, even without this illness, it might be hard for older people to do activities involving fine motor skills. For many people, these changes mean losing the ability to care for themselves. Thanks to modern technologies and aids, we can replace some activities that require fine motor skills.

Only a few prisons and cells are adjusted for the needs of older people, which can cause more issues for older people in the execution of imprisonment. There might be issues with stairs, which older people need to use, or long distances that need to walk to get somewhere. Another example is bathrooms, where there might be missing handles or no manipulating machines, which could help limit the risks of falls.

As Humblet and Decorte (2013) state, life in prison is physically more exhausting, waking up while being called up, lying on the ground, and offers rather physical work ... Prison regime, timetable, activities, and cell control... are adjusted rather to younger prisoners from a physical perspective. The pace seems to be crucial there. Dawes (2009) questions how realistic it is for an older prisoner to get up and dressed for 15 minutes. It seems that the literature supports (Dawes, 2009; Upton, 2014) the idea of separated regimes for older prisoners and younger prisoners in the form of a quitter and safer environment with better accessibility and secure care for older prisoners.

Humblet and Decorte (2013) highlight the thought of institutional consideration in current prisons. Social workers, as workers of social systems, could be thinking and trying to adapt to prison life for prisoners. But these influences are rather a water drop in the sea.

Vidovicova, Wija (2020) raised the main areas of interest for social gerontology and gerontology's intervention, which include:

- ✓ Well-being and quality of life;
- ✓ Social relations, partnerships, and family;
- ✓ Multi-generation relationships in society and ageism;
- ✓ Financial security at higher age;
- ✓ Active ageing: employment, leisure time activities, volunteering;
- ✓ Physical environment: building, public sites, neighbourhood;
- ✓ Spiritual needs: meaning of life, usefulness (to feel needed and useful, to belong somewhere);
- ✓ Issue of mental health such as dementia and overall mental health;
- ✓ Palliative care – care at the end of one's life.

Even though the main reasons for executive imprisonment are to protect society from criminality and to connect protection and prevention in the case of older prisoners, it is crucial to consider to what extent their bio-psycho-physical health is influenced by these changes and how they will change during ageing.

During the execution of imprisonment, unfortunately, an individual is separated from their family and social environment. For sentenced and dismissed, the consequences are stigmatizing. The forgiven person will have to face the challenges of the stigma, which might be more complicated than imprisonment. One of the most influential factors of successful social integration is the functional family environment (Juzl et al., 2016).

Concerning the armed group, it is also essential to mention the professional aspect. Mainly the social workers who work in prisons. The work of these social workers and other skilled workers in prisons deserves recognition and greater attention from professionals and the general public. Care should also be given to the workers themselves, not only in the context of professional development but also in the context of professional therapeutic support and reflection on one's needs and feelings. The challenge is also the reflection of new trends and concepts in social work, where an exemplary use is a multidisciplinary team of which a social worker should be a member (Stárek, Víšek, 2022).

4. Foreign countries experiences

An exciting model originated in Switzerland – in prison Lenzburg, they have created a separate department for prisoners for over 60 years to provide them with needed care.

During the realization of this department in 2011, leaders decided that they would accept only those over 60 years (called 60+) older and were physically or psychologically unable to be settled in the ordinary department of the prison. Even though this department is part of the prison, a certain level of cooperation from older prisoners is expected. This cooperation includes a willingness to be part of the community.

One of the main aims of this department is to keep the cognitive, intellectual and motor skills of older prisoners. Remaining in social contact is also another aim of a structured daily regime to prevent feelings of loneliness. Therefore, a significant part of the day is created for prisoners to be spent in standard rooms, recreational places or in their employment.

Prisoners can arrange an appointment with their general doctors, psychiatrists, psychologists, priests, dentists or any other medical employer. This appointment is afterwards allowed by a prison employee. The available doctor's care includes regular

check-ups, monitoring prisoners' health. The offer involves physiotherapy, movement therapy, medical baths, and discussion groups. Based on their needs, prisoners can also use multifunctional sports halls.

In the department "60+", is the offer of employment limited to half of the day, while the employment offers are adequate to age. Further, employment options are jobs in an office, laundry, cleaning and gardening. Also, every community member must fulfil their duties to the community.

The reflection on the ten years of existence of the department proves a very positive effect. The issue derives mainly from situations when it is complicated to involve prisoners in a daily regime of the community. Their everyday motivation for activities, interaction or cooperation is connected to the reality that after they enter into the community, which is often accompanied by euphoria, there is often stagnation or decrease in motivation. It is not unusual for some prisoners to refuse to cooperate. This only complicates the tasks of the prison's employees. The job is to give prisoners some sense of life even though their vision might be limited or their health conditions are not so good. The successful development of this relationship significantly influences the education of employees, which must be focused on working with older prisoners.

In department "60+", they purposely open the topic of life ageing and its acceptance, dying, acceptance of one's actions, change of life beliefs, or reflection on one's life. This problem is not discussed only with representatives of the church, but it can also be addressed with prison employees. It is always surprising how openly older prisoners talk about dying. During this discuss, many prisoners realize that they will probably die in prison. Therefore, it is not surprising that people outside prisons ask whether it is morally correct to let someone die in prison.

(Graben, Hotz, Holenstein, 2014)

5. Exploratory probe

We reflected the thought and idea of an ageing society. We investigated whether the older prisoners had specialized care and how they were treated. Further, we researched anamnestic and social factors about older prisoners to prove the importance of cross-disciplinary cooperation to provide support, maintenance and help.

However, this probe type demands deeper thinking and sufficient time to provide results. This topic needs to be reflected not only by researchers and participants but also by broader society. We created a picture of these specific groups and their needs. Based on this picture, we can define what type of care needs to be provided to this particular group, not only by prisons and their employees.

6. Preparation and process of interviews

The helping scenario for interviews uses a structure related to the topic derived from general thematical circles. The case of interviews originated from the whole theme of the exploratory probe. The discussion always discussed two main areas. The first area was related to the analysis of the respondent's documentation, which involved information about the social status of the respondent. However, we could not analyze the respondents' medical documentation. The second area is the interview with the respondent. It is important to mention we reflected on the ethics of research. The interviewees participated voluntarily, and their wishes and concerns were reflected, for example, by omitting some topics.

We realized that a structured interview might not provide an accurate picture of the topic, so we prepared some thematical questions, which we followed and supported with extra questions. Thus, the interview had the characteristics of a semi-structured interview.

Overall, we conducted six semi-structured interviews. Respondents agreed to participate in interviews and use the generated data. Similar statements apply to two prisons, which agreed as well. It is crucial to mention that cooperation between researchers and jails results from previous collaboration on different research projects. A total of six semi-structured interviews were conducted. We used a Dictaphone to record the entire interview. Each of the respondents was familiar with the use of this technique, and no one objected to it. If any of the respondents disagreed with a Dictaphone, an option was ready to record the respondents' answers in writing during the interview.

The meetings always took place without the presence of uninvolved third parties. The creation of open contacts was initially induced by all respondents with general questions about the topic. The aim was to gain trust. Creating a friendly atmosphere, tactfulness, and showing reasonable interest in the respondent's testimony helped to a relaxed interview. The questions were formulated neutrally so as not to indicate the expected answer. We strived to ask short questions, if possible, in straightforward sentences. A strategic method was chosen, where the questions started with more general problems/ranges of topics and then focused on particular issues.

The interviewer's task was to ensure that questions were asked in a standardized fashion, with the same emphasis, during all interviews. The analysis of the respondents' reactions, behavior and non-verbal expressions during the interview – body movements, gestures, facial movements, smile, laughter, and gaze – was not overlooked. All six interviews took place without any unexpected or awkward situations that could break the trust between the respondent and the interviewer.

The average time allowance of each interview lasted about 90 minutes.

7. Characteristics of respondents

The aimed group of respondents was not limited by ethnicity, gender, age, religion, education, or sentence length. To be able to answer research questions, we collected answers from specific groups of people. This group involves prisoners who are currently in execution of imprisonment. About the aim of this research, age was the main factor. The minimal age line was 65 years when they conducted their crime.

Table 3
List of respondents

<i>respondent</i>	<i>gender</i>	<i>age</i>	<i>education attained</i>	<i>Marital status</i>	<i>No. of children</i>	<i>Sentenced for</i>	<i>Receiver of social help</i>	<i>Health issues</i>
R no. 1	man	66	Vocational certificate	married	2	Stealing	Yes	No
R no. 2	man	68	Vocational certificate	divorced	2	Rape	Yes	Yes
R no. 3	woman	68	Primary school	single	1	Threaten under drug substance	Yes	Yes
R no. 4	man	70	university – masters’ degree	married	3	Blackmail, stealing	Yes	Yes
R no. 5	man	73	A-levels	widower	3	Neglecting of maintenance obligation	Yes	Yes
R no. 6	man	79	Primary school	married	2	obstructing the execution of an official decision	Yes	Yes

8. Summary of the research probe

The focus group in this research included six older prisoners. In context, this number of six prisoners is a probe rather than a general result. The age of respondents had to be over 65 when conducting their crime for us to be able to include them in our research. The bigger number of our participants comprised participants between 65 and 70 years old when committing their crime (in total, four respondents in our research). One respondent was 73 years old, and the last respondent was 79 years old.

Respondents – conductors of crime were sentenced for diverse crimes such as stealing, blackmailing, neglecting of maintenance obligation, threatening under drug substance, obstructing the execution of an official decision, and rape. Every respondent was previously sentenced – the number of previous sentences was between 1 and 3 for each respondent. Gender: There was a bigger number of males, as there were five male respondents and only one female.

All respondents were Czech, and none of them was foreign. Further, if we consider the marital status of respondents, two of them were divorced (2 males), two were married (2 males), one was widower (male), and one was single (female), but she was in long-term relationships with her partner.

We can compare it with other studies. For example, Mäsiarova (2019) presents data from 2017 in her study. Half of the respondents were single, and with a big difference, there were groups of divorced prisoners. The difference between the presented probe and Mäsiarova's (2017) study could be explained by the significant age difference between respondents, as the older generation prefers to get married than the younger generation.

In the context of family situation, all respondents have children, and their number differs from 1 to 3. They are already adults. Family relationships were not the topic of this probe, even though they provided exciting information. With regards to the influence of imprisonment, it is crucial to mention a study conducted by Danek (2023), who claims that parents' imprisonment has a significant negative influence on children in several aspects of their lives. He noticed influence mainly in children's psychological sphere and social competencies. It is important to reflect that our group of children and young adults was influenced not only by the imprisonment of their parents but also by the fact their housing is an institutional organization – a prison.

Achieved education is very diverse for our respondents. This information was verified by the respondents and through the analysis of their documentation. Two respondents have finished primary school; two had vocational certificates – one in selling and one in plumbing; one obtained A-levels at an economic academy, and one completed university with a master's degree in pedagogy.

Further, it is essential to mention the financial situation of respondents. All of them are receiving social help from the state for older people. Unfortunately, we have not found out the amount of this social help. However, all respondents agreed that more is needed for them and their families. Further, all the respondents agreed that they have financial issues derived from loans that they could not pay back during their productive age. Thus, they have financial issues which bind them. Two respondents stated they do not have any material possessions due to their financial situation or due to the influence of their family.

Another exciting area which appeared during interviews was the health condition of respondents. Except for one respondent, all of them have complained about their physical or psychological issues, which sometimes overlapped. Some of the older prisoners were addicted to alcohol, substances, or drugs. The respondents themselves stated that the health issues are related to their age. Overall, the health issues included movement problems, cardiovascular issues, diabetes, higher cholesterol, hypertension, etc.

According to Zverinova (2022), older people (including people in excursion of imprisonment) often experience chronic illnesses. The number of psychological issues is also high. It is expected that 30% of elderly people struggle with their mental health.

9. Conclusion

With regard to the recent trend in the ageing population in the Czech population, we can assume that in the near future, there will be significant growth in the number of elderly people committing crimes. Thus, there will be a growth in the number of older people in the excursion of imprisonment. This population will be burdened with personal, health, and social issues for which society and the prison service of the Czech Republic must prepare (Martinkova, Biedermanova, 2019).

The number of older prisoners is not big, but the majority of care providers in prisons have noticed them. Sometimes, it is not viewed as a significant issue. Diverse studies (Branham, 2010; Snyder, 2009) highlight that prisoners might look ten years older than they are. The connection between health and physical appearance cannot be forgotten, and this is also related to prisoners. Cognitive levels, recidivism and years spent in prison are only a few risk factors which influence prisoners. Compensation and the mechanism (physical mechanism) of support, help, and care can help make prisoners more comfortable with ageing.

What do we need to pay attention to in prisons so that ageing is more comfortable for older prisoners? The job market in prison is limited and primarily focused on physical jobs. Job and daily activities are often the main motive of life in prison, not only for older prisoners. Analysis of health care for this group and development of health care is missing here. On top of our interest must be physical health issues. Any health limitation cannot be omitted by prison employees, and mainly any mental decline and potential signs of dementia. Hand in hand with psychological issues, there is also an issue with loneliness. To successfully develop and prevent these issues, it is crucial to provide quality education for employees. So, the employees will be aware of all potential issues related to ageing.

According to Vidovicova and Wiji (2020), we can say that if an individual is locked up in an environment without any positive attitude and any chance for contact with positively tuned people, there is not any chance for them to change their attitude and behavior. Therefore, we must overcome negativity with a positive attitude, behavior, and mindset without judging previous life experiences.

Further, discussing other aspects of this life stage, such as palliative care or the spiritual needs of prisoners and their relatives, is crucial. It is essential to focus more on prisoners' needs, which can change with ageing, but they do not need to be acknowledged by them, their environment, and by the prison's employees.

With regards to the expansion of this age group, it is vital to keep analyzing this age group not only through the lenses of social care but also through the amount of care and support they need.

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